

STUDIES IN THE CYCLOPENTANE SERIES. PART II.
EXPERIMENTS TOWARDS THE SYNTHESIS OF
WIELAND'S C₁₃-ACID IN PROPER
STEREOCHEMICAL FORMS.*

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A method for the synthesis of 8-ethoxy-8-(1:5-dimethylhexyl)-4-methylvaleric acid is described.

In continuation of the earlier communication (Dutta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 611) the following experiments have been performed to complete the synthesis of Wieland's C₁₃-acid (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 134, 276 ; 216, 91) and as a preliminary to it the acid (I) has been synthesised. From this acid by following the method developed in part I an acid of the constitution (II) is expected with the carboxyl groups in the *trans* position, *i.e.*, same as that in the C₁₃-acid.

The isopropyl group in (II) can be oxidised by chromic acid according to the well known method of Windaus (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 117, 146 ; 126, 277) to give the desired tricarboxylic acid (I). Attempts have been made to prepare the ketone (III), the acid chloride (IV) and the ketone (V) which might be utilised for the synthesis of (I).

The action of methylheptyl magnesium iodide on ethoxyethyl cyanide leads not to (III) but to a hydrocarbon. The formation of Grignard's reagent from ethoxyethyl iodide is also abnormal.

The acid chloride (IV) can not be prepared by the action of thionyl chloride and pyridine on the corresponding acid as the lactone (VI) is formed. To prepare this acid, methylheptyl iodide has been condensed with malonic

* A preliminary note appeared in *Science and Culture*, 1941, 7, 316.

A series of unsuccessful or incomplete attempts are recorded in literature, *e.g.* Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1546 ; 1933, 811, 815 ; Bardhan, *Science and Culture*, 1937, 3, 654 ; Banerjee, *ibid.*, 1938, 3, 678.

In all these formulae

ester in presence of sodium ethoxide and ethoxyethyl residue has been introduced through the potassium derivative in xylene solution. This has been hydrolysed to the half ester by heating with an excess of concentrated potassium ethoxide solution (Marshall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2337) and the second ester group has been hydrolysed by the addition of the calculated quantity of water and heating on the water-bath (Claisen, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 703). The dicarboxylic acid is decarboxylated. The successive replacement of the hydrogen atoms of acetoacetic ester with the heavy substituents methylheptyl and ethoxyethyl in order to produce (V) shows that in whichever order the condensation is attempted, the second condensation does not take place.

The ketone (V) has, however, been obtained by the action of magnesium methyl iodide under the conditions described by Feiser (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1444, 2482) on the nitrile (VII), which has been prepared thus: methylheptyl iodide has been reacted with cyanoacetic ester in presence of sodium ethoxide with very good yield and the product condensed with ethoxyethyl iodide in presence of potassium in xylene solution. Partial hydrolysis of the disubstituted cyanoacetic ester has been carried out quantitatively by methyl alcoholic potash and on decarboxylation on heating, the substituted nitrile (VII) has been obtained in good yield.

Attempts to prepare the cyanohydrin from this ketone (V) with liquid hydrocyanic acid having failed, it was reduced with amyl alcohol and sodium. The secondary alcohol (VIII), isolated in the usual way, was converted into chloride with thionyl chloride and pyridine. Replacement of the chlorine atom with iodine by boiling with sodium iodide in alcoholic solution leads to the elimination of hydrogen chloride with the formation of the unsaturated compound (IX). The same compound was also obtained while attempting to replace the chlorine atom with cyano group. The desired acid (I) has been obtained through the action of carbon dioxide on the Grignard's complex from the chloro compound. The acid has been purified through its ethyl ester. It is observed that when the concentration of the sulphuric acid in esterification is increased, the ester is contaminated with the lactone (X).

It was expected that this acid (I) should lead to the lactone (X) by the action of pyridine and thionyl chloride and from this lactone, the dibromo ester, necessary for the formation of the cyclopentane ring, will be easily obtainable. This method has, however, led to a neutral product containing halogen and having a higher boiling point than is expected of this lactone. The reaction might have proceeded abnormally (*cf. J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2488) and the product has not been further investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl (1:5-Dimethyl)-hexylacetoacetate.—To a well cooled solution of sodium (16 g.) in alcohol (220 c.c.) was added with shaking a mixture of acetoacetic ester (96 g.) and methylheptyl iodide (158 g.). After allowing it to come to the room temperature and then refluxing on the water-bath for 24 hours, it was decomposed with ice and acid. It was then extracted with ether and washed with sodium bicarbonate, dried and distilled at 122°/4 mm., yield 105 g. It had a characteristic smell. (Found: C, 69.5; H, 10.5. $C_{14}H_{26}O_2$ requires C; 69.4; H, 10.7 per cent),

Ethyl β-Ethoxyethyl-(1:5-dimethyl)-hexylacetoacetate.—Methylheptyl acetoacetic ester (50 g.) was added drop by drop with thorough shaking to an ice-cold suspension of finely powdered potassium (8 g.) in xylene. On standing overnight a clear solution was obtained. To this was added ethoxyethyl iodide (45 g.) with shaking. After heating the mixture on the water-bath for 12 hours, it was refluxed for 24 hours in an oil-bath at 160°. It was then decomposed with ice and thoroughly washed with acid and alkali. After removal of xylene, a small quantity of the high boiling residue was left. This was distilled and two fractions were collected, one boiling at 138-42°/3.5 mm. and the other boiling at 158-60°/3 mm. The former fraction (2.3 g.) on analysis was found to agree with the theoretical values and did not give any ferric chloride colouration. (*Found: C, 68.46; H, 10.8; C₁₈H₃₄O₄ requires C, 68.76; H, 10.8 per cent).

Ethyl (1:5-Dimethyl)-hexylmalonate.—It was prepared in the usual way by allowing malonic ester (45 g.) to react with methylheptyl iodide (45 g.) in alcoholic sodium ethoxide solution (4.5 g. sodium and 80 c.c. of alcohol). The reddish solution was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried and distilled at 128°/4 mm., yield 39 g. (Found: C, 65.7; H, 9.96. C₁₅H₂₈O₄ requires C, 66.1; H, 10.2 per cent).

Ethyl (1:5-Dimethyl)-hexyl-β-ethoxyethyl malonate.—To finely powdered potassium (5.1 g.) under xylene was added with shaking methylheptyl malonic ester (37 g.). The formation of the potassium salt was complete on standing overnight. Next it was treated with ethoxyethyl iodide (30 g.) drop by drop. It was heated on the water-bath for 6 hours and for 40 hours again at 150° in the oil-bath. The solution was worked up in the usual way and the residue, left after removal of xylene, was distilled 150-65°/5 mm. This on redistillation passed over at 154-58°/5 mm., yield 22 g. Very careful fractionation was necessary to remove low boiling fractions. (Found: C, 66.36; H, 10.32. C₁₇H₃₂O₅ requires C, 66.2; H, 10.4 per cent).

(1:5-Dimethyl)-hexylbutyrolactone (VI).—The above disubstituted malonic ester (26 g.) was treated in the cold with an alcoholic solution of potassium (9.5 g.) in alcohol (65 c.c.). It was allowed to stand overnight and then heated on the water-bath for 24 hours. Water (4.5 c.c.) was then added with shaking and then heating under reflux was continued for another 24 hours. This time crystalline potassium salt separated. The second ester

* Microanalysis by Mr. N. N. Ghosh.

group was hydrolysed by adding water (4.5 c.c.) and heating for another 12 hours. On addition of water, a clear reddish solution was obtained and this was thoroughly extracted with ether to remove any diester, if any, from the solution. The aqueous solution was strongly acidified whereby a heavy oil separated on the surface. It was extracted with ether. The residue, left after the removal of ether, was gradually heated to 220° and kept at that temperature for 1 hour until there were no visible signs of evolution of any gas. It was cooled and a solution of sodium carbonate was added. The alkaline solution was again extracted with ether to remove any mono-ester and the aqueous portion was again acidified with hydrochloric acid, when a heavy oil separated on the surface. It was extracted with ether and on evaporation of ether the residual oil was decolourised with animal charcoal in petroleum ether solution when a mobile oil (15 g.) was obtained having a slight yellowish tinge. This was thoroughly dried and dissolved in benzene and was treated with pyridine (5.3 g.) and thionyl chloride (6.5 c.c.) at low temperature. It was allowed to stand in ice overnight and at the ordinary temperature for 24 hours. Next the clear upper layer was decanted off and distilled when a mobile oil was obtained boiling at 126°/5 mm. having a milky appearance, yield 10 g. It was poured into water and charcoaled when a clear sweet-smelling mobile oil was obtained at 125°/4 mm. The oil was found to be insoluble in sodium carbonate, but soluble in dilute sodium or potassium hydroxide solution from which it could be regenerated by acidification. From concentrated alkaline solution, sodium or potassium salt separated. (Found: C, 72.86, 72.7; H, 10.7, 10.7. $C_{12}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 72.7; H, 11.1 per cent).

Ethyl (1:5-Dimethyl)-hexylcyanoacetate.—A mixture of cyanoacetic ester (30 g.) and methylheptyl iodide (45 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (4.8 g.) in alcohol (95 c.c.). On refluxing on the water-bath for 12 hours, the red solution was decomposed with ice and the ethereal solution was washed with acid and alkali. On working up in the usual way the cyano ester was obtained, b. p. 125°/5 mm. yield 34.3 g. (Found: N, 6.6. $C_{12}H_{22}O_2N$ requires N, 6.2 per cent).

Ethyl β -Ethoxyethyl-(1:5-dimethyl)-hexylcyanoacetate.—Methylheptyl cyanoacetic ester (34 g.) was added to potassium (5.7 g.) under xylene at 0° drop by drop. On standing overnight a clear solution was obtained. This was cooled in ice and to this ethoxyethyl iodide (35 g.) was added with shaking. The mixture was allowed to stand in ice for 4 hours and at the ordinary temperature for another 4 hours. Next it was heated on the water-bath for 12 hours and in an oil-bath at 160° for 16 hours. The solution was then decomposed with ice and acid. The xylene solution was dried and distilled

at 160-170°/7 mm. On redistillation, it passed over at 165°/7 mm., yield 36 g. (Found: N, 5.1. $C_{17}H_{31}O_2N$ requires N, 4.7 per cent).

(1:5-Dimethyl)hexyl-β-ethoxyethylacetonitrile (VII).—Methyl alcohol (150 c.c.) and the above ester (60 g.) were added to a solution of potassium hydroxide (12 g.) dissolved in the smallest quantity of water. The mixture warmed up and after thorough shaking it was allowed to stand overnight. Next day it was heated on the water-bath for 5 hours. After cooling the mixture was saturated with carbon dioxide. Methyl alcohol was evaporated off and then water added. Traces of neutral matter were removed with ether and the cyano-acid isolated by extracting the acidified solution with ether. The solvent was removed on the water-bath and on heating the residue to 220°, carbon dioxide was evolved. Decarboxylation was complete within an hour. The nitrile, thus obtained, distilled at 127°/5 mm, yield 36 g. (Found: N, 6.6. $C_{14}H_{27}ON$ requires N, 6.2 per cent).

Methyl α-(1:5-Dimethylhexyl)-γ-ethoxypropyl ketone (V).—The above nitrile (22 g.) in dry benzene (100 c.c.) was added all at once to a warm solution of methyl magnesium iodide from magnesium (4.8 g.) and methyl iodide (15 c.c.) containing benzene. After heating on the water-bath for 8 hours it was poured into ice, when a white crystalline solid separated in addition to magnesium hydroxide. After addition of hydrochloric acid, it was refluxed for 4 hours and then subjected to steam distillation. The distillate and the residue in the flask were extracted with benzene and on working up in the usual way, a clear mobile oil having a characteristic smell was obtained boiling at 118°/4 mm. No semicarbazone could be prepared from this ketone and it gave a very slight test for nitrogen. (Found: C, 75.3; H, 12.0. $C_{18}H_{36}O_2$ requires C, 74.4; H, 12.4 per cent).

α-Ethoxy-γ-(1:5-dimethylhexyl)-δ-hydroxypentane (VIII).—The above ketone (18 g.) was dissolved in dry isoamyl alcohol (225 c.c.) and sodium (18 g.) was added. The mixture was heated until the whole of it had gone into solution (about 5 hours). It was diluted with water, amyl alcohol distilled in steam, and the cold solution was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed with water and dilute hydrochloric acid. Finally it was dried and distilled at 126°-30°/4 mm, as an oil having a rather unpleasant smell, yield 12 g. (Found: C, 73.7; H, 13.1. $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$ requires C, 74.1; H, 12.9 per cent).

α-Ethoxy-γ-(1:5-dimethylhexyl)-δ-chloropentane.—A benzene solution of the above alcohol (12 g.) was treated with pyridine (4 g.), thionyl chloride (5 c.c.) in the cold. On standing overnight the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 3 hours. On working up in the usual way, it passed over at 122-24°/5 mm., yield 12 g. It contained little sulphur which was removed

by refluxing with precipitated copper. (Found: Cl, 12.8. $C_{12}H_{21}OCl$ requires Cl, 13.56 per cent).

α-Ethoxy- γ -(1:5-dimethylhexyl)- Δ^7 -pentene (IX).—(a) The above chloro compound (12 g.) was heated with mercuric cyanide (24 g.) on the water-bath for 1 hour. There was no reaction. Next it was heated in an oil-bath for 3 hours at 160-70°. The substance gradually turned brown. After extraction with benzene, it was finally distilled in *vacuo* when a clear mobile oil boiling at 94°/5 mm. was obtained, yield 6 g. During the latter part of the distillation, volatile mercury compounds began to distill which were removed with hydrogen sulphide in benzene solution. (Found: C, 79.16; H, 13.0. $C_{18}H_{30}O$ requires C, 79.67; H, 13.2 per cent).

(b) The above chloride (22 g.) was refluxed on the water-bath with sodium iodide (26 g.) and alcohol (25 c.c.) and water (1 c.c.) for 24 hours. The mixture gradually became homogeneous. After 24 hours, further alcohol (25 c.c.) was added and the heating continued for another 6 hours. On working up in the usual way, it was found that almost the whole of the product passed over at 95°-103°/6 mm., yield 16 g.

δ-Ethoxy- β -(1:5-dimethylhexyl)-*α*-methylvaleric Acid (I).—A mixture of the above chloride (15 g.) in ether (15 c.c.) was added to a mixture of magnesium (2.6 g.) in ether (30 c.c.) containing methyl iodide (3 c.c.) at such a rate that the vigour of the reaction was maintained. After the reaction was over, it was refluxed on the water-bath for 3 hours and a current of dry carbon dioxide was passed for 2 hours into the mixture cooled with a freezing mixture. The temperature was kept during this period below -10°. There was a separation of two layers and the mixture was decomposed with ice-cold sulphuric acid. The ethereal extract was separated and washed with a dilute solution of potassium hydroxide. On acidifying the alkaline solution an oil separated having a slight rancid odour. It was extracted with ether and on removal of the solvent, it was dried in vacuum, yield 5.5 g. The above acid (2.5 g.) was esterified with a mixture of alcohol (25 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (1.5 c.c., *d* 1.84) for 12 hours on the water-bath. On working up in the usual way, the substance boiled at 150-55°/7 mm., yield 2 g. (Found: C, 71.7, 72.1; H, 11.6, 11.7. $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$ requires C, 72.0; H, 12.0 per cent).

The above acid (10 g.) was esterified with alcohol (50 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (7 c.c., *d* 1.84) for 12 hours. On working up in the usual way, a product was isolated (8 g.), b.p. 151-55°/6 mm. This on analysis was found to consist of a mixture of the ethyl ester and the corresponding lactone arising from de-ethoxylation. The latter lactone was not appreciably

soluble in cold alkali. (Found: C, 73.3; H, 11.3. $C_{16}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 72.0; H, 12.0. $C_{14}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 74.3; H, 11.4 per cent).

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